

Studies on the Properties of Prostaglandin Synthetase of Caprine Seminal Vesicles

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The prostaglandin (PG) synthetase complex in the microsomal fraction of caprine (goat) seminal vesicles was found to have the highest PGE₂ synthetase activity in comparison to that in similar other animal sources. The results of the investigations on the kinetics of PGE₂ synthesis, factors influencing product formation, cofactor requirement and stability of the enzyme system show that the PG-synthetase complex from goat vesicular gland was very unstable, and its properties were generally comparable to that from the highly active ovine seminal vesicular multienzyme complex.

Prostaglandins are important bioregulators of the mammalian systems in which they take part in various essential physiological processes. After Vane's discovery in 1971 that aspirin, the well-known non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID), acts by inactivating PG-synthetase complex¹, the PG-synthetase system is extensively used now-a-days for screening of all newly synthesised NSAIDs.

The microsomal fractions of ovine² and bovine³ seminal vesicular glands well-known as rich sources of PG-syn-

thetase, which, as a multienzyme complex (MES), is responsible for the biosynthesis of PGs. We have studied extensively the goat (caprine) vesicular gland microsomes as a source of PG synthetase, in comparison to bovine, ovine, rat and guineapig sources. Fig. 1 shows the biosynthetic pathway of major biologically active PGs via a common cyclic-endoperoxide intermediate by oxygenation of arachidonic acid (C20 : 4, n-6)⁴.

In this study, we primarily investigated the optimum conditions necessary for the conversion of arachidonic acid to PGE₂ by microsomal PG-synthetase complex of goat vesicular glands, which has not been studied previously from this source, using radiochromatographic and spectrophotometric assay methods.

Results and Discussion

Detection of a suitable source : In search of suitable source for PGE₂ biosynthesis, we collected seminal vesicular glands of different animals such as sheep, goat, rat and guineapig, and measured the PGE₂ synthetase activity spectrophotometrically in their microsomal fractions. On comparing the PGE₂ synthetase activities, we found that the goat vesicular gland was by far the richest source of PGE₂ biosynthesis as shown in Table 1.

Detection of the products of arachidonate oxygenation : Several products that resulted from oxygenation of arachidonic acid by PG-synthetase system of goat vesicular microsomes are shown in Fig. 1. We measured the rates of formation of the major biologically important PGs arising from the cyclic-endoperoxide intermediate PGH₂. The three major PGs, viz. PGE₂, PGF_{2α} and PGD₂ were measured quantitatively by determining the radioactivity in the spots corresponding to their respective non-radioactive standards on the chromatogram, using radiolabelled [³H] arachidonic acid as the substrate in these experiments.

Factors influencing product formation and distribution :
pH : To determine the pH optima for the biosynthesis of PGE₂ by the goat vesicular microsomes, we used three

Fig 1 Biosynthesis of prostaglandins via cyclo-oxygenase pathway in caprine seminal vesicles

TABLE 1—COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PG-SYNTHEASE SOURCE

Animal	Tissue	nmol PGE ₂ formed/ mg protein/min
Bovine	Seminal vesicles	6-7
Ovine	Seminal vesicles	10-13
Caprine	Seminal vesicles	30-45
Rat	Seminal vesicles	11-13
Guineapig	Seminal vesicles	12-14
Fish (fresh water):	Stomach, Intestine	0.15-0.2
<i>Magur</i>	Liver	0.11-0.15
<i>Telapia</i>	Kidney	0.12-0.14

buffer systems, viz. tris-HCl, potassium phosphate and imidazole-HCl. In all the three cases the rate of formation of PGE₂ at different pH values were estimated by spectrophotometric method. Phosphate and imidazole buffers were superior to tris-buffer at lower pH values. But, their efficiency decreases with increase in pH and also they could not be used above pH 7.8, due to their limited buffering capacity. As shown in Fig. 2, the rate of PGE₂ formation in tris-buffer reached a maximum value at pH 8.2, after which it decreased sharply. Thus the optimum pH for PG synthetase activity in 100 mM tris-HCl buffer was found to be 8.2.

Substrate concentration : Substrate saturation curves

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on PGE₂ biosynthesis by goat vesicular microsomes. PGE₂ was assayed spectrophotometrically using potassium phosphate 0.1 M, tris-HCl 0.1 M and imidazole-HCl 0.1 M buffers at different pHs. All incubations were done at 37° for 3 min with the standard incubation mixture changing only the buffer system.

for the biosynthesis of PGE₁ and PGE₂ using homo-v-linolenic acid (C20 : 3, n-6) and arachidonic acid (C20 : 4,

Fig. 3. Effect of substrate concentration on the rate of PGE₁ and PGE₂ synthesis by goat vesicular microsomal fraction. The standard incubation mixture was used with varying concentrations of homo-v-linolenic acid and arachidonic acid as substrates. PGE₁ and PGE₂ formed were measured spectrophotometrically.

n-6) as substrates respectively, are shown in Fig. 3. Sharp activity maxima were obtained for the substrates homo-v-linolenic acid and arachidonic acid at 0.4 and 0.5 mM respectively. This shows a well-defined substrate affinity for the biosynthesis of each type of PGEs. Again, the rates of formation of PGE₂ and PGF_{2α} and PGD₂ were determined by the radiochromatographic assay method, using [³H]-labelled arachidonic acid as substrate, at 0.4 and 0.8 mM concentrations. Table 2 shows that at 0.4 mM arachidonic acid, PGE₂ is formed at a much higher rate than PGF_{2α} and PGD₂. While at 0.8 mM arachidonic acid concentration, PGE₂ biosynthesis is decreased with a concomitant increase in the rates of PGF_{2α} and PGD₂ formation. So not only a substrate specificity but also substrate affinity of the PG-synthetase complex is important for the biosynthesis of a specific PG.

Cofactor requirement : Optimum conditions necessary for PG-biosynthesis by goat vesicular microsomes with different externally added cofactors were studied. As with bovine and ovine systems, caprine system also needed reduced glutathione with epinephrine, each at a concentration of 5 mM for the most effective combination of cofac-

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SUBSTRATE CONCENTRATION ON PG SYNTHESIS

Arachidonic acid mM (cpm/nmol)	PG formed nmol/mg protein/min		
	PGE ₂	PGF _{2α}	PGD ₂
0.8 (2.5 × 10 ⁴)	16.8	5.5	2.6
0.4 (5 × 10 ⁴)	28.0	2.7	0.9

PG synthesis measured by radiochromatographic assay.
Incubation mixture was the same as described in Table 1 except for the change in concn. of [³H]-labelled arachidonic acid as shown.

tors (Fig. 4). Although hydroquinone could replace epinephrine, and NADPH or ascorbic acid could replace glutathione (reduced) as cofactors for PGE₂ biosynthesis, but they were not very effective. The cofactor requirement for the biosynthesis of the three major PGs obtained by arachidonate oxygenation is presented in Table 3.

Protein concentration and time : The curve obtained by plotting the protein (enzyme) concentration against the rate of PGE₂ formation showed a linear relationship (Fig. 5a), i.e. the product formed increased linearly with increase in enzyme concentration. When the rate of PGE₂ formation

Fig. 4. Effect of epinephrine and glutathione on the rate of PGE₂ synthesis by goat vesicular microsomes. The standard incubation mixture was used but concentrations of epinephrine and reduced glutathione were varied. PGE₂ formed was measured spectrophotometrically.

was plotted against time, a non-linear kinetic curve was obtained (i.e. the kinetics of PGE₂ formation does not obey the classical Michelis-Menten equation), where an apparent linearity was observed only for the first 3 min. This deviation of linearity is typical of the kinetics of PG formation catalysed by PG-synthetase complex⁵ (Fig. 5b). The decrease in product formation was due to the auto-inactivation of the PG-synthetase complex, as it is referred to as a suicidal enzyme⁶

Stability : PG synthetase is a very unstable enzyme complex and it rapidly undergoes auto-inactivation even at -20°. The half-life at -20° was found to be about 48 h. In

TABLE 3—REQUIREMENTS OF COFACTORS FOR THE BIOSYNTHESIS OF PGE₂, PGF_{2α} AND PGD₂

Sl. no.	Reaction mixture **	PG formed (nmol/mg protein/min)		
		PGE ₂	PGF _{2α}	PGD ₂
1.	Complete system	26.37	12.11	6.84
2.	-GSH, -Epinephrine	0.51	0.08	0.12
3.	-Epinephrine	5.49	1.62	0.89
4.	-GSH	14.82	3.60	0.89
5.	-GSH, -Epinephrine, +Hydroquinone (5)	7.42	4.47	0.82
6.	-GSH, +Hydroquinone (5)	20.17	6.90	3.23
7.	-GSH, -Epinephrine, +Ascorbic acid (5)	0.29	0.21	0.27
8.	-GSH, +Ascorbic acid (5)	15.02	5.61	1.72
9.	-GSH, -Epinephrine, +NADPH (0.2)	0.56	0.03	0.01
10.	-GSH, +NADPH (0.2)	11.001	4.59	1.04

* Data obtained by radiochromatographic assay. ** Complete system contained 1 mM [³H]-arachidonic acid (9 × 10³ cpm/nmol), 5 mM glutathione, 5 mM epinephrine, 100 mM tris-HCl (pH 8.2) and 6.5 μg of protein per 5 μl assay mixture. (+) or (-) denotes addition or subtraction of component from the complete system; number within parenthesis denotes mM concn. of the component in the reaction mixture.

our efforts to stabilise the enzyme we found that Ca²⁺ ion either in solution or in suspension stabilises the enzyme complex. In the presence of Ca²⁺ ion, half-life of the PG-

Fig. 5. Effect of (a) incubation time and (b) protein concentration on PGE₂ synthesis in goat vesicular microsomes at 37° : (a) all tubes contained the standard incubation mixture and 0.3 mg of the microsomal protein and (b) all tubes contained the standard incubation mixture but the protein concentration was varied; incubation time, 3 min.

synthetase in goat seminal vesicular microsomes shifted from 2 to 12 days, as reported earlier⁷. Hence from the experiments reported here it could be concluded that the optimum concentrations necessary for the reactants in the mixture for the formation of all the three PGs (PGE₂, PGF_{2α} and PGD₂) catalysed by goat vesicular microsomal suspension in 100 mM tris-HCl (pH 8.2) are as follows : 1 mM arachidonic acid, 5 mM epinephrine and 5 mM glutathione. Maximal rate of PG production under the above condition when the reaction was carried out at 37°, could be sustained only for 3 min after which the rate would fall precipitously.

Experimental

Arachidonic acid, homo- ν -linolenic acid, epinephrine bitartrate, tris, imidazole and reduced glutathione (Sigma), [^3H]-labelled arachidonic acid (Amersham International), silica gel G (E. Merck) and standard PGs (gift sample) were used. All other reagents and solvents used were of analytical grade. Vesicular glands from an Indian variety of goat (*Capra hiscus*) were collected fresh from a local abattoir.

The standard incubation mixture was composed of a substrate, (arachidonic acid or homo- ν -linolenic acid) 1 mM; epinephrine, 5 mM; glutathione (reduced), 5 mM; tris-HCl, pH 8.2, 100 mM; and appropriate amount of goat vesicular microsomal suspension in a total volume of 500 μl .

Preparation of microsomes : All operations were performed at 0–4°. Seminal vesicular glands were trimmed off excess fat, diced and blended in a Waring blender for 2 min with two volumes of 100 mM tris-HCl, pH 8.2. The homogenate was centrifuged for 10 min at 12000 g. The supernatant thus obtained was passed through a double layer of cheese cloth and centrifuged at 100000 g for 1 h. The resulting microsomal pellet was suspended in one volume of 100 mM tris-HCl, pH 8.2 and this was used as the enzyme source⁸.

The protein content of the microsomal fraction was determined by Lowry's method⁹.

Spectrophotometric assay : PG-synthetase activity was assayed by the reported method¹⁰ by measuring the amount of PGE₁ or PGE₂ formed. The standard incubation mixture containing either arachidonic acid or homo- ν -linolenic acid as substrate was incubated for 5 min at 37° with shaking. The reaction was initiated by addition of microsomal suspension (0.3 mg protein) as enzyme source and terminated by the addition of 100 μl of 2 N HCl. The PGE formed was extracted in ethyl acetate and converted to PGB by alkaline isomerisation and absorbance was measured at 278 nm. The PG-synthetase activity was expressed in nmoles of PGE formed/min/mg protein under standard assay conditions.

Radiochromatographic assay : The incubation mixture

was the same as in spectrophotometric method, only the substrate being replaced by 1 mM (5, 6, 8, 9, 11, 12, 14, 15- ^3H) arachidonic acid having a specific activity of 1.8×10^4 cpm/nmol, in a total volume of 10 μl . After incubation at 37° for 5 min the reaction was stopped by adding 2 μl of 2 N HCl and 5 μl aliquots from each assay tube was spotted on silica gel G, tlc plates. The tlc plates were chromatographed in the following solvent system ethyl acetate-water-isooctane-acetic acid, 11 : 10 : 5 : 2 (upper layer). Standard PGs (cold) in the visible concentration range were spotted over each spot to facilitate the detection of [^3H] PGs. Then PGE₂, PGF_{2 α} and PGD₂ were detected by exposing the plates to iodine vapour or spraying with anisaldehyde reagent¹¹. PGs were scraped off the tlc plates into scintillation vials and radioactivity was counted in a liquid scintillation counter (Beckman).

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